

Kinetics and Mechanism of Cerium(IV) Oxidation of Dextrose and Sorbose in Aqueous Sulphuric Acid Medium

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The kinetic study of Ce^{IV} oxidation of dextrose and sorbose in aqueous sulphuric acid medium shows first order kinetics with respect to both Ce^{IV} as well as the substrate. The reaction rate decreases on increasing the concentration of hydrogen ion concentration. The variation of sulphate ions shows retarding effect on the reaction rate. The values of activation energy have been calculated and a suitable mechanism best fitting to our kinetic data is proposed.

KINETIC studies of Ce^{IV} oxidation of organic compounds have been widely and extensively probed¹⁻⁶, but none has attempted to study Ce^{IV} oxidation of dextrose and sorbose. The present communication deals with the kinetic study of cerometric oxidation of dextrose and sorbose in the temperature range of 35 to 50°. The main aim has been to explore the complete mechanism of cerometric oxidation of sugars.

Experimental

Dextrose, sorbose, ceric ammonium sulphate, potassium iodide, sodium thiosulphate, ferrous ammonium sulphate, starch and potassium sulphate used were of AnalaR (B.D.H.) grade, and sulphuric acid of Oster.

Method: A standard stock solution of sodium thiosulphate was prepared⁷. Ceric ammonium sulphate solution was prepared in H_2SO_4 (4 N) and was standardised with standard sodium thiosulphate solution. The reaction was initiated by adding a solution of substrate to the reaction mixture

containing required amount of ceric ammonium sulphate, sulphuric acid, potassium sulphate (used to keep the ionic strength constant) and water, and maintained at the desired temperature with the help of an electrically heated thermostat with an accuracy $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The kinetics were followed by removing 5 ml aliquot from the reaction mixture at different intervals of time and quenched it into 10 ml aqueous KI solution (5%) to arrest the reaction. The unreacted ceric ammonium sulphate was determined against standard sodium thiosulphate solution using starch as an indicator. The method gave reproducible results.

Results and Discussion

Many-fold variation of ceric ammonium sulphate and sugars concentrations indicates first order dependence of the reactions on Ce^{IV} and both the substrates, dextrose and sorbose (Table 1, Fig. 1). The retarding effects of sulphuric acid and ionic strength of the medium (Table 1) have been recorded. The effect of added sulphate ions

Fig. 1

TABLE-1

Temp. = 40° (unless otherwise mentioned)

[Ce ^{IV}] × 10 ⁴ M	[Dex]* × 10 ² M	[Sor]* × 10 ² M	[H ₂ SO ₄] M	Ionic strength μ M	-dc/dt × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹
0.29	5.00	—	5.00	1.50	0.17
0.57	5.00	—	5.00	1.50	0.50
1.16	5.00	—	5.00	1.50	0.98
2.30	5.00	—	5.00	1.50	1.42
0.12	—	1.00	5.00	1.50	0.06
0.22	—	1.00	5.00	1.50	0.06
0.48	—	1.00	5.00	1.50	0.16
1.05	—	1.00	5.00	1.50	0.27
2.50	0.50	—	5.00	1.50	0.47
2.50	1.00	—	5.00	1.50	0.73
2.50	1.60	—	5.00	1.50	1.15
2.50	2.50	—	5.00	1.50	1.60
2.50	5.00	—	5.00	1.50	2.50
2.00	—	0.25	5.00	1.50	0.24
2.00	—	0.30	5.00	1.50	0.31
2.00	—	0.68	5.00	1.50	0.75
2.00	—	1.25	5.00	1.50	1.41
2.00	—	2.50	5.00	1.50	2.00
2.20	2.50	—	0.50	1.50	1.37
2.20	2.50	—	1.30	1.50	0.75
2.20	2.50	—	2.10	1.50	0.60
2.20	2.50	—	2.90	1.50	0.40
2.00	—	1.00	0.50	1.50	0.50
2.00	—	1.00	1.30	1.50	0.38
2.00	—	1.00	1.70	1.50	0.98
2.00	—	1.00	2.50	1.50	0.28
2.25	2.50	—	5.00	1.62	1.55
2.25	2.50	—	5.00	1.81	1.27
2.25	2.50	—	5.00	1.84	0.88
2.25	2.50	—	5.00	1.92	0.68
2.00	—	1.00	5.00	1.50	1.00
2.00	—	1.00	5.00	1.59	0.50
2.00	—	1.00	5.00	1.84	0.98
2.00	—	1.00	5.00	1.91	0.30
2.00	5.00	—	5.00	1.50	0.62 ^a
2.00	5.00	—	5.00	1.50	0.85 ^b
2.00	5.00	—	5.00	1.50	1.63 ^c
2.00	5.00	—	5.00	1.50	2.22 ^d
2.00	—	1.00	5.00	1.50	0.50 ^a
2.00	—	1.00	5.00	1.50	0.70 ^b
2.00	—	1.00	5.00	1.50	1.35 ^c
2.00	—	1.00	5.00	1.50	1.75 ^d

* Dex = Dextrose, Sor = Sorbose.

^a 35°, ^b 40°, ^c 45°, ^d 50°.

indicates that the reaction rates decrease with the increasing concentration of sulphate ions.

The reaction rate was markedly affected by the rise in temperature (Table 1). The values of energy of activation of dextrose and sorbose oxidations were found to be 13.71 and 21.02 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively.

A perusal of literature⁸⁻¹⁰ on Ce^{IV} oxidation in sulphuric acid shows complex formation with sulphate ions, viz. CeSO₄²⁺, Ce(SO₄)₂ and Ce(SO₄)₂²⁻ species. Some equilibria involving HCe(SO₄)₂²⁻, H₂Ce(SO₄)₂²⁻, H₃Ce(SO₄)₂²⁻ and H₄Ce(SO₄)₂²⁻ ions have also been suggested¹¹ to explain the mechanism of certain reactions. Our observations lead to assume that Ce(SO₄)₂ is the reactive species of Ce^{IV} in sulphuric acid. On the basis of results following mechanism is suggested.

where M = dextrose and sorbose.

$$\text{Now, } \frac{-d\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}}{dt} \rightarrow = \text{K}_2[\text{X}] + \text{K}_3[\text{Radical}][\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] \quad (1)$$

On applying steady state principle,

$$\frac{d[\text{X}]}{dt} = \text{K}_1[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{M}] - \text{K}_{-1}[\text{X}] - \text{K}_2[\text{X}] = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{or, } [\text{X}] = \frac{\text{K}_1[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{M}]}{(\text{K}_{-1} + \text{K}_2)} \quad (3)$$

On applying steady state principle,

$$\frac{d(\text{Radical})}{dt} = \text{K}_2[\text{X}] - \text{K}_3[\text{Radical}][\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or, } \text{K}_2[\text{X}] = \text{K}_3[\text{Radical}][\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] \quad (5)$$

On putting the value of K₃[Radical][Ce^{IV}] in equation (1)

$$\text{we get, } \frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \text{K}_2[\text{X}] + \text{K}_3[\text{X}]$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = 2\text{K}_2[\text{X}] \quad (6)$$

On substituting the value of X from equation (3) to the equation (6) we have

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{2\text{K}_1\text{K}_2[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{M}]}{\text{K}_{-1} + \text{K}_2} = \text{K}[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{M}] \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where } \text{K} = \frac{2\text{K}_1\text{K}_2}{\text{K}_{-1} + \text{K}_2}$$

Thus, (i) the reaction follows first order kinetics with respect to Ce^{IV}, (ii) the order of reaction with respect to dextrose and sorbose is unity, and (iii) the reaction rate decreases by increasing the hydrogen ion concentration.

In ceric oxidation, it has been confirmed that the inhibitory action is produced^{8,9} due to HSO₄⁻ ion autocatalytic activity¹⁰ of HSO₄⁻ ion is explained by assuming that the reactive ceric sulphate species, Ce(SO₄)₂ is removed by the following reactions,

If various forms of ceric sulphate are held in rapid equilibrium, the concentration of H₂Ce(SO₄)₂²⁻ ion will be proportional to the total Ce^{IV} present in the reaction mixture.

$$\text{Hence, } [\text{Ce(SO}_4)_2] = \frac{[\text{H}_2\text{Ce(SO}_4)_2^{2-}]}{\text{K}'\text{K}''[(\text{HSO}_4^-)]}$$

Thus, ceric(IV) sulphate would gradually convert to H₂Ce(SO₄)₂²⁻, and hence the reaction velocity

would decrease with the increase of ceric ammonium sulphate concentration because $H_2Ce(SO_4)_2$ is the unreactive species. Similarly, with the increase of sulphuric acid concentration the reaction velocity would also decrease.

Stoichiometry and product study : From the thin layer chromatographic technique it has been possible to identify the actual oxidation product of dextrose and sorbose, the final products being formic acid and carbon dioxide. One mole of dextrose or sorbose requires 13.0 mole of Ce^{IV} ions :

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